

THE PROCEDURE FOR DETERMINING THE PERSONAL INCOME TAX BASE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY AND ITS ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT.

In this article, in the context of the tax reforms carried out in our republic today, about the income tax from individuals, in particular, the procedure and characteristics of determining the base of this tax, the types of factors affecting the base, and, moreover, based on in-depth analysis, the existing problems have been identified and the necessary proposals have been made.

Key words: tax base, tax object, personal income tax, tax relief, deductions, tax policy, cost.

Introduction.

The determination, calculation and collection of any tax is related to the determination of the taxable base[1]. In fact, in order to determine the amount of tax to be paid, in addition to determining the object of taxation, it is necessary to determine the tax rate and other elements of taxation, the specific value of the economic base of the tax in relation to it. For example, the tax base is the most important component of the tax elements and is a delicate asset, which has been studied for a long time in the world tax system and is considered an actual concept these days.

If we look at the economic policy of our country, we can see that these days, fundamental development of the tax system and policy, increasing the efficiency of tax administration, and at the bottom of it, consistent reduction of the tax burden and further expansion of the tax base are one of the main tasks facing the system. Therefore, the essence, importance and principles of the procedure for determining the income tax base of individuals play an important role in ensuring the performance of the above-mentioned tasks. After all, the correct and effective implementation of the income tax procedure, and its fair determination, is an important factor that determines the well-being of the population, as well as the level of social protection. Based on this, we identified this process as the object of research in this article.

Analysis and results.

The tax base of existing taxes in the tax system of our republic and the procedure for determining it are given in detail in the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2]. In particular, if we talk about personal income tax. The procedure for determining the personal income tax base is also considered an important support for the effective operation of the state budget. As a result of our research, we are witnessing that according to the statistics of the last years, the share of this tax has a sufficient contribution to the total tax revenues.

Determining the base of personal income tax is determined by the following steps[4]. We have illustrated these processes through this diagram:

Figure 1. The procedure for determining the base of personal income tax.

Source: Compiled by the author based on the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Based on Figure 1, the first step in the process of determining the tax base of individuals is to determine the total income of these individuals. In this case, the total income of individuals is divided into four groups according to the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. At the second stage, it is necessary to deduct from these incomes the incomes that are not subject to taxation according to the Tax Code, and at the third stage, the amount of tax benefits should be deducted[3].

According to the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, tax benefits play an important role in determining the personal income tax base, and these benefits are grouped as follows:

Table 1.

Grouping of tax benefits that are deductible when determining the personal income tax base in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

№	Privilege type	Aspects of application of the privilege
1	Non-taxable income (Article 378 of the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan)	Financial aid amounts; amounts of full or partial reimbursement of the cost of referrals by the tax agent; sums paid by the employer for the provision of outpatient and (or) inpatient medical services to its employees and their children; income from performing temporary one-time jobs, etc.

2	Exemption of natural persons from taxation (Article 378 of the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan)	Heads and employees of diplomatic missions of foreign countries, officials of consular institutions, their family members living with them, if they are not citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan - on all their income from sources in the Republic of Uzbekistan, except for income not related to diplomatic and consular service, etc..
3	Reduction of the total income of certain categories of taxpayers (according to Article 378 of the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taxpayers are partially exempted from taxation (on incomes in the amount of 1.41 times the minimum wage for each month in the month in which the income was received))	Persons awarded the titles "Hero of Uzbekistan", Hero of the Soviet Union, Hero of Labor, persons awarded with the Order of Fame of all three levels; disabled persons and participants in war, as well as persons equal to them, whose scope is determined by legislation; persons with disabilities since childhood, as well as persons with group I and II disabilities; single mothers with two or more children under the age of sixteen; widows and widowers who have two or more children under the age of sixteen and who do not receive a survivor's pension, etc.

Source: Compiled by the author based on the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Grouped tax benefits listed in Table 1 cover the most basic deductions in the tax system of our republic in determining the income tax base and are an important support in the social protection of taxpayers.

As you can see, in the process of determining the personal income tax base given above, the aspects that we should pay attention to are what kind of income is included in the base, what kind of income is not recognized as income and the scope of benefits[5].

In addition to these, there are several factors that affect the expansion or contraction of the income tax base, and we can see these factors in the table below.

Table 2.

Factors affecting the personal income tax base.

№	An influencing factor
1.	Changes in the tax policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan
2.	Changes in tax rates
3.	Granting or cancellation of tax benefits
4.	Expansion or contraction of the tax object
5.	Change in the amount of income of the taxpayer
6.	Changes in types of non-taxable income
7.	Changes in types of income exempt from taxation
8.	A change in the amount due to a reduction in the total income of certain categories of taxpayers

Source: table compiled by the author

Analyzing the data given in Table 2, the above influencing factors can be directly or inversely related to the tax base. In particular, the tax rate is inversely related to the tax base, and an increase in the rate leads to the concealment of income, which, in turn, leads to a decrease in the tax base. If the granting of tax benefits causes a decrease in the tax base, the cancellation or reduction of the benefits leads to an increase in the tax base. In addition, if the

increase in non-taxable, tax-exempt types of income, the increase in the amount related to the reduction of the total income of certain categories of taxpayers directly leads to the reduction of the tax base, their reduction causes the expansion of the base.

The influencing factor related to the tax base is the change in the amount of income of the taxpayer, that is, if the total income of the taxpayer increases, the tax base expands, and vice versa, if the amount of income decreases, the tax base decreases.

In the process of analysis, we are convinced that the procedure for determining the income tax base of individuals in the tax system of our republic is quite complicated and there are many factors affecting it. During our research, we studied the tax procedures of our country, as well as the experiences of foreign countries.

Looking at the tax experiences of foreign countries, the main focus is on the type of income and the amount of expenses in the process of determining the income tax base of individuals. For example, if we consider the French tax system. The French government uses income tax to implement its social policies. In this case, income tax is used to encourage the family and help the owners of small property in the conditions where social consumption rates are not well developed. Residents of France pay all their income at home and abroad (including contracts) as their tax base. Its peculiarity is that the tax is collected not from the personal income of an individual, but from the total income of the family. Expenditures specifically defined by legislation are excluded from the taxable base. Including special support for nutrition. Certain exclusions are set for certain social groups: elderly people, disabled people, etc.

In France, taxpayers' income is calculated based on the following 7 categories[6]:

1. Wages of employees;
2. Land revenue (Rental of land and buildings);
3. Income from working capital (dividends and interest);
4. Income from resale (building, securities);
5. Income from production and trade activities of non-joint-stock companies;
6. Non-commercial income (income of self-employed persons);

When determining the tax base, expenses related to finding the total income are deducted. In particular, the following are deducted from the total income in land revenue:

1. 15% when renting a building and 10% when renting land;
2. Costs of using the building;

Amount of taxes on buildings and land. It can be understood from the above that in the French tax system, the procedure and features of determining the income tax base of individuals are somewhat complex and multifaceted, that is, it is based on the system of supporting the activities of taxpayers.

Conclusion

Based on our analysis, we came to the conclusion that the procedure for determining the personal income tax base in the tax system of our republic includes three stages, and the first step is to determine the total income of individuals, and the second stage is to separate the income that is not subject to tax according to the SK. and in the third step, the amount of tax credits should be deducted. These deductions are the most important part in determining the tax base, and the characteristics of social incentives for taxpayers or tax avoidance are embodied in this part. If the deductions are not given adequately or fairly, it creates situations like tax evasion. In this regard, we believe that some tax benefits in our tax system are not

enough. For example, we propose to include the following exemptions when paying tax on income from property rental: Мол-мулк объектини ижарага беришдан олинган дармадан бу объектга қилинган харажат миқдорини чегириш лозим;

1. Land and property taxes should be considered as expenses and deducted from income tax when renting property.

2. Based on the mentality and religious characteristics of our country, the expenses incurred for Hajj and Umrah pilgrimages should be considered as non-taxable income.

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